

spindle pole body 25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid : 0000-0001-7027-5788

104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Abstract

Background : A kinetochore is a protein structure that attaches during cell division to pull sister chromatids apart via spindle fibers and is associated with duplicated chromatids in eukaryotic cells. It assembles on the centromere and links the chromosome to microtubule polymers from the mitotic spindle during mitosis and meiosis. The NDC80 complex is a central kinetochore heterotetramer protein complex that is important for chromosome congression and spindle checkpoint signaling. SPC25 is one of the 4 proteins that has been identified to be present in NDC80 complex. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of SPC25, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might

*ML dicoveries of SPC25 synergy in Meningiomas

Email address: sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com (shriprakash sinha)

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pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: SPC25, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Meningioma	2
1.1.1 World Health Organization (WHO) classification	2
1.1.2 Historical perspective	3
1.1.3 Pathophysiology	4
1.2 spindle pole body 25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25)	4
1.3 Insight behind the work	5
1.4 Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	6
2 Methods	6
2.1 Static data from Patel et al. [1]	6
2.2 Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	6
2.3 Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	7
2.4 Regarding biological insight	8
3 Results & Discussion	8
3.1 SPC25 related synergies	8
3.1.1 FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3] .	8
3.1.2 SPC25 unknown combinations with high ranking	9
4 Conclusion	12
5 References	14

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [4]). As of 2021, there

exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [5]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [6] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [7], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [8] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [9]. Finally, Cushing [10] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [13] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [11] and Pamir et al. [12]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. spindle pole body 25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25)

Janke et al. [14] showed that the budding yeast proteins NDC80p, NUF2p, SPC24p and SPC25p interacted at the kinetochore. In chromatin immunoprecipitation experiments, they found that NDC80p, NUF2p, SPC24p and SPC25p associated with centromere DNA, and SPC24 interacted genetically with MCM21 encoding a kinetochore component. Further, they observed that although conditional lethal *spc24-2* and *spc25-7* cells formed a mitotic spindle, the kinetochores remained in the mother cell body and failed

to segregate the chromosomes. Despite this defect in chromosome segregation, *spc24-2* and *spc25-7* cells did not arrest in metaphase in response to checkpoint control.

McClelland et al. [15] purified the xNDC80 complex to homogeneity from *Xenopus* egg extracts and identified two novel interacting proteins. Further, they concluded that these are the functional homologs of the yeast SPC-24/25 proteins based on limited sequence similarity, common coiled-coil domains, kinetochore localization, similar phenotypes, and copurification with xNDC80 and xNUF2. Using both RNAi and antibody injection experiments, they extended the previous characterization of the complex and found that SPC-24/25 are required to establish and maintain kinetochore-microtubule attachments and metaphase alignment. They also showed that SPC-24/25 was required for chromosomal movement to the spindle poles in anaphase.

To understand the function of the NDC80 complex, using an immunoaffinity approach, Bharadwaj et al. [16] identified two novel subunits of the human NDC80 complex, termed human SPC25 (hSPC25) and human SPC24 (hSPC24). They observed that hSPC25 interacted with human homolog of yeast NDC80 (HEC1) throughout the cell cycle and localized to kinetochores during mitosis. Through a series of experiments they proved that hSPC25 was an essential kinetochore component that played a significant role in proper execution of mitotic events.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [17] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [18] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [18].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [19]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as

per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [20], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [17] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [17]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [21], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based

sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional plane, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. SPC25 related synergies

Note - SPC25 was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2^{nd} order combinations of SPC25 were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [3]

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [3] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they

defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Vasudevan et al. [3] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma and they also defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1), DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B) and Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of SPC25 with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t SPC25. CDCA5 - SPC25 shows high ranking of 220 (laplace), 55, 245 (rbf), 209 (jansen); CENPF - SPC25 shows high ranking of 209 (laplace), 207 (linear), 184 (rbf), 124; KIF18B - SPC25 shows high ranking of 166 (laplace), 134 (linear), 166 (rbf), 6; and TOP2A - SPC25 shows high ranking of, 161 (laplace), 255 (linear), 139 (rbf), 119;

While, CKS2 - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 151, 143, 92, 28; TPX2 - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 205, 140, 131, 181; CCNB2 - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 20, 164, 117, 72; TROAP - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 127, 80, 206, 20; TK1 - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 63, 229, 124, 171; BUB1B - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 39, 156, 65, 61; KIF4A - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 226, 124, 171, 84; NEK2 - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 146, 43, 158, 112; BRIP1 - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 246, 13, 113, 186; DEPDC1B - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 14, 19, 37, 53; and HJURP - SPC25 shows low ranking of, 125, 206, 157, 49.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t SPC25 with SPC25 – > CDCA5 / CENPF / KIF18B / TOP2A.

3.1.2. SPC25 unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by SPC25, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [1]. I document here, the 2^{nd} order combinations with SPC25, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the SPC25 and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, reticulocalbin 1 (RCN1), phosphofructokinase, platelet (PFKP), scavenger receptor class B member 1 (SCARB1), centromere protein M (CENPM), ring finger protein 32 (RNF32), non-SMC condensin I complex subunit G (NCAPG), TTK

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS SPC25

RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T SPC25				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - SPC25	151	143	92	28
TPX2 - SPC25	205	140	131	181
TOP2A - SPC25	161	255	139	119
CCNB2 - SPC25	20	164	117	72
CDCA5 - SPC25	220	55	245	209
TROAP - SPC25	127	80	206	20
TK1 - SPC25	63	229	124	171
BUB1B - SPC25	39	156	65	61
CENPF - SPC25	209	207	184	124
KIF4A - SPC25	226	124	171	84
NEK2 - SPC25	146	43	158	112
KIF18B - SPC25	166	134	166	6
BRIP1 - SPC25	246	13	113	186
DEPDC1B - SPC25	14	19	37	53
HJURP - SPC25	125	206	157	49

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between SPC25 VS Individual members.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t SPC25	
CDCA5	SPC25
CENPF	SPC25
KIF18B	SPC25
TOP2A	SPC25

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between SPC25 and Individual members.

protein kinase (TTK), centromere protein F (CENPF), kinesin family member 14 (KIF14), prostate transmembrane protein, androgen induced 1 (PMEPA1), hypoxia inducible factor 3 subunit alpha (HIF3A), immunoglobulin superfamily, member 2/CD101 molecule (CD101), neuron navigator 1 (NAV1), centrosomal protein 55 (CEP55), cartilage intermediate layer protein (CILP), TOPBP1 interacting checkpoint and replication regulator (TICRR), NUF2 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (NUF2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), solute carrier family 16 member 12 (SLC16A12), pleckstrin homology and RhoGEF domain containing G4B (PLEKHG4B), coiled-coil domain containing 144C, pseudogene (CCDC144CP), H2B clustered histone 5 (HIST1H2BD), H4 clustered histone 8 (HIST1H4H), zinc finger protein 233 (ZNF233), coiled-coil domain containing 78 (CCDC78), solute carrier family 9 member C2 (putative) (SLC9C2), G protein-coupled receptor 146 (GPR146), insulin like growth factor 2 (IGF2), chromatin licensing and DNA replication factor 1 (CDT1), establishment of sister chromatid cohesion N-acetyltransferase 2 (ESCO2), ETS variant transcription factor 4 (ETV4), cyclin N-terminal domain containing 1 (CNTD1), DnaJ heat shock protein family (Hsp40) member C22 (DNAJC22), carbonic anhydrase 8 (CA8), H2A clustered histone 6 (HIST1H2AC), H2B clustered histone 4 (HIST1H2BC), neurexophilin 4 (NXPH4), RNF32 divergent transcript (LINC01006), collagen type XVIII alpha 1 chain (COL18A1), immunoglobulin superfamily member 5 (IGSF5), H2B clustered histone 21 (HIST2H2BE), NDUFA4 mitochondrial complex associated like 2 (NDUFA4L2), H1.2 linker histone, cluster member (HIST1H1C), smoothelin like 2 (SMTNL2), solute carrier family 38 member 3 (SLC38A3), apolipoprotein D (APOD), solute carrier family 30 member 10 (SLC30A10), hydroxycarboxylic acid receptor 1 (HCAR1), mitochondrially encoded tRNA-Trp (UGA/G) (MT-TW), tripartite motif containing 59 (TRIM59), firre intergenic repeating RNA element (FIRRE), killer cell lectin like receptor K1 (KLRK1), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 887 (LINC00887), lipocalin like 1 (LCNL1), PITX1 antisense RNA 1 (C5orf66), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 954 (LINC00954), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A8, pseudogene (ANKRD20A8P), deleted in lymphocytic leukemia 2 (DLEU2), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1564 (LINC01564), small Cajal body-specific RNA 7 (SCARNA7), uroplakin 3B (UPK3B), RRS1 divergent transcript (RRS1-AS1), and high mobility group box 1 pseudogene 21 (HMGB1P21), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [1]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of SPC25 with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t SPC25.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t SPC25 with SPC25 – > RCN1 / PFKP / SCARB1 / CENPM / RNF32 / NCAPG / TTK / CENPF / KIF14 / PMEPA1 / HIF3A / CD101 / NAV1 / CEP55 / CILP / TICRR / NUF2 / CDCA5 / SLC16A12 / PLEKHG4B / CCDC144CP / HIST1H2BD / HIST1H4H / ZNF233 / CCDC78 / SLC9C2 / GPR146 / IGF2 / CDT1 / ESCO2 / ETV4 / CNTD1 / DNAJC22 / CA8 / HIST1H2AC / HIST1H2BC / NXPH4 / LINC01006 / COL18A1 / IGSF5 / HIST2H2BE / NDUFA4L2 / HIST1H1C / SMTNL2 / SLC38A3 / APOD / SLC30A10 / HCAR1 / MT-TW / TRIM59 / FIRRE / KLRK1 / LINC00887 / LCNL1 / C5orf66 / LINC00954 / ANKRD20A8P / DLEU2 /

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS SPC25									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T SPC25									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
RCN1 - SPC25	178	121	227	214	PFKP - SPC25	190	2	175	145
SCARB1 - SPC25	158	148	211	172	CENPM - SPC25	180	158	173	219
RNF32 - SPC25	156	239	194	58	NCAPG - SPC25	157	18	244	175
TTK - SPC25	160	222	202	132	CENPF - SPC25	209	207	184	124
KIF14 - SPC25	147	168	221	91	PMEPA1 - SPC25	110	228	177	202
HIF3A - SPC25	191	147	135	160	CD101 - SPC25	249	39	238	205
NAV1 - SPC25	176	251	165	95	CEP55 - SPC25	217	108	246	159
CILP - SPC25	152	71	144	155	TICRR - SPC25	239	169	147	180
NUF2 - SPC25	181	118	137	183	CDCA5 - SPC25	220	55	245	209
SLC16A12 - SPC25	257	105	204	253	PLEKHG4B - SPC25	247	233	127	215
CCDC144CP - SPC25	200	79	231	150	HIST1H2BD - SPC25	242	217	257	240
HIST1H4H - SPC25	170	203	196	206	ZNF233 - SPC25	245	141	219	204
CCDC78 - SPC25	207	234	192	44	SLC9C2 - SPC25	237	244	251	255
GPR146 - SPC25	224	172	162	141	IGF2 - SPC25	252	173	258	232
CDT1 - SPC25	222	210	128	139	ESCO2 - SPC25	171	159	119	202
ETV4 - SPC25	185	227	164	13	CNTD1 - SPC25	210	180	107	200
DNAJC22 - SPC25	216	149	181	250	CA8 - SPC25	243	128	188	221
HIST1H2AC - SPC25	162	183	200	143	HIST1H2BC - SPC25	169	160	160	62
NXPH4 - SPC25	250	120	215	225	LINC01006 - SPC25	218	174	129	233
COL18A1 - SPC25	212	171	193	21	IGSF5 - SPC25	148	90	208	169
HIST2H2BE - SPC25	173	96	237	157	NDUFA4L2 - SPC25	172	170	234	51
HIST1H1C - SPC25	194	59	240	226	SMTNL2 - SPC25	228	130	256	256
SLC38A3 - SPC25	232	257	239	140	APOD - SPC25	214	196	236	133
SLC30A10 - SPC25	211	50	218	228	HCAR1 - SPC25	233	215	224	174
MT-TW - SPC25	213	162	77	165	TRIM59 - SPC25	192	212	146	135
FIRRE - SPC25	186	245	212	220	KLRK1 - SPC25	244	125	255	238
LINC00887 - SPC25	138	208	232	198	LCNL1 - SPC25	256	240	122	248
C5orf66 - SPC25	199	237	97	146	LINC00954 - SPC25	163	211	167	177
ANKRD20A8P - SPC25	258	101	254	246	DLEU2 - SPC25	15	193	203	187
LINC01564 - SPC25	206	187	172	78	SCARNA7 - SPC25	154	256	145	191
UPK3B - SPC25	254	225	205	149	RRS1-AS1 - SPC25	135	189	186	45
HMGB1P21 - SPC25	143	219	250	218					

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between SPC25 VS Individual members.

LINC01564 / SCARNA7 / UPK3B / RRS1-AS1 / HMGB1P21.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic SPC25 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of SPC25-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t SPC25	
RCN1 / PFKP / SCARB1 / CENPM / RNF32 ...	
NCAPG / TTK / CENPF / KIF14 / PMEPA1 ...	
HIF3A / CD101 / NAV1 / CEP55 / CILP ...	
TICRR / NUF2 / CDCA5 / SLC16A12 / PLEKHG4B ...	
CCDC144CP / HIST1H2BD / HIST1H4H / ZNF233 ...	
CCDC78 / SLC9C2 / GPR146 / IGF2 / CDT1 ...	
ESCO2 / ETV4 / CNTD1 / DNAJC22 / CA8 ...	
HIST1H2AC / HIST1H2BC / NXPH4 / LINC01006 ...	
COL18A1 / IGSF5 / HIST2H2BE / NDUFA4L2 / ...	
HIST1H1C / SMTNL2 / SLC38A3 / APOD / ...	
SLC30A10/ HCAR1 / MT-TW / TRIM59 / FIRRE ...	
KLRK1 / LINC00887 / LCNL1 / C5orf66 / ...	
LINC00954 / ANKRD20A8P / DLEU2 / LINC01564 ...	
SCARNA7 / UPK3B / RRS1-AS1 / HMGB1P21	SPC25

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between SPC25 and Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

5. References

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